

IMPROVING THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ROLE OF MICROORGANISMS IN ENVIRONMENTAL PROTECTION IN THE MIND OF STUDENTS

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Annotation. Today, the important role of microorganisms in environmental protection is one of the modern problems, it is necessary to form in the minds of students the concepts of intensification of production processes, increase of producers with high productivity, creation and implementation of effective biotechnological methods.

Introduction: Modern society requires the educational system to educate highly qualified, ambitious, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals. In the 2017-2021 action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the task of "educating a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, creating a reserve of competent scientific and pedagogical personnel in higher education institutions" was set. Accordingly, the technology of processing plant waste, citrus fruit waste, whey, and also agricultural animal waste is one of the important issues in biotechnology. Accumulation of this type of waste in some places has a serious impact on environmental pollution.

Many wastes and by-products can be recycled. According to information, about 1,700 million of various spiky plants. t. straw comes out and most of it is not used. Or, only 20% of pineapple is used in canning, and most of it goes to waste. Its fruit, peel and other waste are crushed to get juice, and the dried remains are fed to cattle. It is possible to reduce the amount of waste discharged from these factories with alcohol fermentation.

Biotechnological processes associated with the exchange of various organic substances during fermentation pollute the environment both chemically and biologically. According to studies conducted in the early 1970s, fermentation used in pharmaceuticals was highlighted as the main source of contamination. For example, this idea was mainly derived from observing the activities of antibiotic companies. Fermentation wastes are microbial cells of certain metabolic products and unused components of the nutrient medium.

Carbohydrate-containing waste and by-products can be processed by conventional microbial digestion or biotechnological processes. For example, molasses, which is the starting syrup for crystallization of sucrose and is removed from the technological cycle, is a by-product of sugar production. In addition to sugar, it contains sulfites, carbonates and calcium and magnesium salts. Not all of the remaining sugar is used during the fermentation of molasses.

Starch makes up 50% of the dry mass of other plant grains, potatoes and cassava. This product is mainly obtained from johor, potato and cassava. It is easily subjected to acid or enzymatic hydrolysis and dextrin and glucose are obtained from it. These hexoses are used to produce alcohol and fructose syrup.

Cellulose and hemicellulose can be subjected to microbial degradation and conversion to obtain ethyl alcohol or raw materials for the chemical industry. The cellulase and hemicellulase genes contained in *Clostridium thermosellum* can be transferred to other species of *Slostridium*,

and cellulose and hemicellulose can be converted into ethyl alcohol, acetone, vinegar and lactic acid.

Bioconversion is the conversion of metabolites into similar compounds with the help of microbial cells. At the same time, microorganisms affect a certain stage of important and complex processes of chemical synthesis.

An ancient type of bioconversion is the process of obtaining vinegar, which is the conversion of ethyl alcohol into acetic acid.

Bioconversion is unique because it is associated with one type of reaction and a certain structure (stereospecificity). Bioconversion to isopropanol-acetone, glycerol-dihydroacetone, L-tyrosine-L-dioxyphenylalanine, glucose-gluconic acid and finally to 2-ketoglucon or 5-ketogluconic acid and is converted to sorbitol-L-sorbose. The bioconversion of sorbitol to sorbose is the only biological reaction in the chemical industry.

Steroid hormones were synthesized using methods based on bioconversion. In the early 1930s, Kendall and Reichstein isolated cortisone from the adrenal gland, which was used to treat rheumatoid arthritis. The first intermediate product of cortisone synthesis is progesterone. Bioconversion is carried out in an aqueous environment at a temperature of 37°C and atmospheric pressure. Currently, it is possible to hydrolyze the carbon atom of the steroid nucleus with the help of certain microorganisms and obtain the desired steroid.

Microorganisms are also used in the production of raw materials (such as sterols) to obtain steroids.

In some cases, the sequential addition of mixed cultures or microbial strains is necessary to achieve bioconversion. Each of these performs its own stage of bioconversion. The use of immobilized cells increases the efficiency of bioconversion compared to enzymes and reduces its consumption.

2 methods are used to apply strains of microorganisms used in industry: screening of strains and mutations in specific regions of DNA to overcome difficulties in isolation. induction; genetic engineering and the addition of protoplasts to augment the natural reproductive process; methods of creating recombinant DNA are used to transfer natural genes and reconstruct new genes.

Increasing the number of copies of a certain gene in microbial cells is carried out by gene amplification, and as a result, the production of the product encoded by this genome increases dramatically. This technical approach is related to increasing the number of plasmids in the cell. There are usually 1-30 copies per cell and 2-250 genes. At the same time, plasmid genes are increased to 3000 copies in the cell. The process of gene amplification has been well studied in E.coli and is widely used. So far, it has been possible to transfer any chromosomal gene or group of genes into a plasmid, and then transfer the plasmid to Escherichia coli for amplification. In addition, the transfer of genes from one cell to another was carried out by transformation in the presence of polyethylene glycol. In this way, some genes were also transferred to the Bacillus plasmid. Pseudomonas plasmids were transferred to other gram-negative bacteria. This method is used very effectively in biotechnology. For example, it is possible to obtain a large amount of antibiotics in this way.

Conclusion: Increasing the number of copies of a certain gene in microbial cells is carried out by gene amplification, and as a result, the production of the product encoded by this genome increases dramatically. This technical approach is related to increasing the number of plasmids in

the cell. Currently, thousands of strains of microorganisms belonging to hundreds of species are used in the microbiology industry. These strains of microorganisms were originally isolated from natural sources based on their beneficial properties and their properties were improved using various methods. In order to increase the type and quality of products produced in the microbiology industry, continuous research is being carried out on the use of new types of microorganisms.

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